

Dynamic Gesture Recognition Sign Language Interpreter

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Abstract—Hand gestures, body postures, and body movements are all part of sign language, which has been the first and millions of people's sole language for a long time. However, for them to interact with others, the other person must also understand these sign language. Everyone is drawn to the digital lifestyle in this ever evolving environment due to technological breakthroughs. As a result, the issue of online communication for deaf and mute individuals who are only accustomed to sign language has emerged. In order to enable the computer to detect, understand, and translate sign language for the necessary task, a sign language recognition system must be developed. This can be accomplished by applying machine learning methods. In this paper we tried to take images of sign language and fed those images to sign language interpreter. Interpreter is designed in python to convert hand sign videos into corresponding text percentage. From that percentage the alphabet will be recognized. Then using Google text to speech it is converted into audio. Thus sign language interpreters developed by us can be used efficiently for dumb and deaf people.

Index Terms— Human Computer Interaction, Hidden Markov Models, Dataset, Hand gestures, Camera capture, Artificial Intelligent sign language.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interpreters of sign language are essential in establishing communication channels between people who might not have otherwise interacted. By making use of their services, communication becomes reciprocal and needs and desires can be clearly communicated even in the absence of spoken language. Bilingual experts with training in translating sign language into the local tongue are known as sign language interpreters. Helping people experience the target language as naturally as if it were the source language is their aim. In nations like the US, sign language is taught in early childhood education and occasionally as a second language. In nations like the US, sign language is taught in early childhood education and occasionally as a second language. Teachers who are fluent in sign language create an inclusive learning environment by using it to instruct pupils who are hard of hearing. To demonstrate their professional

competence, some educators even have American Sign Language (ASL) credentials.

Sign language interpreters help a variety of professionals, such as physicians, attorneys, social workers, and others, communicate effectively with those who are hard of hearing. Sign language interpreters are essential in fields where accurate and trustworthy communication is essential, such as healthcare and legal services.

In order to properly communicate with people who are deaf or hearing impaired, medical aid, emergency helplines, police departments, auto repair help lines, and other national and international services rely on sign language interpretation. In these situations, it's critical to communicate quickly and accurately, and sign language interpreters facilitate seamless exchanges. Businesses operate across a variety of groups and cultures in today's globalized globe. Employing sign language interpreters guarantees inclusiveness and seamless communication between professionals with hearing impairments. Businesses may reach their full potential and create a diverse workplace by offering equitable opportunities and information access.

Sign language interpreters help deaf attendees participate in presentations, discussions, and performances at public events like conferences, seminars, and cultural gatherings. In emergency situations where effective communication is vital, sign language interpreters are indispensable. They assist deaf people in court, at doctor's appointments, and while interacting with law enforcement. Object detection and recognition is one of the main uses of machine learning in image processing. Machine learning algorithms can learn to recognize and find things of interest in fresh photos by training models on labeled images that contain these objects, such as vehicles, people, or buildings. This feature has important applications in domains such as surveillance, where automated object detection can help spot irregularities or possible dangers. Classifying images is another way that machine learning is used in image processing.

Machine learning algorithms can learn to categorize new photos into the right categories by training models using labeled photographs from various categories, such as landscapes, animals, or medical images. This feature is especially helpful in fields like healthcare, where precise and

Automated image classification can support treatment, planning, medical imaging analysis, and disease diagnosis.

The goal of this project is to create sign language interpreter in order to address the afore mentioned issue. This interpreter makes it possible for a computer to identify American Sign Language (ASL) signs and translate the interpreted information into text for later use. The primary sign language used by Deaf populations in the United States and the majority of Anglophone Canada is American Sign Language (ASL), a natural language. Using both manual and non-manual characteristics, ASL is a comprehensive and structured visual language.

Camera capture is used for gesture recognition, and the input consists of pictures of language signs and motions. HCI, or human-computer interaction, is used for the processing. Human-computer interaction (HCI) is a multidisciplinary field that focuses on the design and use of computer and mobile technology, with a focus on the interaction between people and systems:

HCI aim is to design systems that effectively meet users' needs by understanding how humans interact with technology.

HCI draws on multiple disciplines, including computer science, cognitive science, psychology, sociology, ergonomics, graphic and industrial design, and educational sciences. It has four main components: the user, task, tools/interface, and the context.

HCI has many applications, including speech recognition technology, which is used in chatbots and virtual assistants like Amazon's Alexa, Microsoft's Cortana, Google's Google Assistant. The field that primarily studies how people interact with computers is called human-computer interaction.

The goal of this project is to create a sign language interpreter for dumb and deaf people to communicate efficiently with the societal environment. This interpreter makes it possible for a computer to identify American Sign Language (ASL) signs and translate the interpreted data into text for further use. Camera capture is used for gesture recognition, and the input consists of pictures of language signs and motions. HCI, or human-computer interaction, is used for the processing.

2. Dataset Preparation

In Indian Sign Language, we have produced a dataset of 26 English alphabets. Two distinct people with various hand forms and lighting circumstances execute each sign move. A camera was used to record the movies, which were then divided into individual photos frame by frame, cropped to 100 frames, and then enhanced to produce roughly 250 images for each sign. Following that, the data was split into 1200 photos for testing and 4800 images for training.

Fig-1: Sign language interpreter flowchart

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies have been conducted on deep learning translation of Indian Sign Language. A few of them employed an instrument-based strategy, while others employed a video-based strategy.

Author Name and Year of publication	Journal/Conference Name	TitlePage	Findings	Gap
Omkar Vedak1, Prasad Zavre2, Abhijeet Todkar3, Manoj Patil4	International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)	Sign Language Interpreter using Image Processing and Machine Learning	The feature vector produced in the above step is fed into an image classifier.	Generates human-like voices [22].
Shreya Daga;Atharva Dusane;Dyuti Bobby	International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)	Indian Sign Language Detection and Alert System	artificial neural network enables the system to acquire the capability of learning and identifying various signals	Alert System [21].
M.Aarthi,P.1 Vijayalakshmi 2 Published in International Conference on...8April 2016 Computer Science, Engineering	FIFTH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RECENT TRENDS IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY	SIGN LANGUAGE TO SPEECH CONVERSION	SENSOR-BASED SYSTEM	THE CAST AND REQUIRED HARDWARE IS MAXIMUM IN THIS PROJECTS. WE WILL MOVE TO THE SOFTWARE SYSTEM [4].

Table I:-Literature Review

4. Sign language to speech conversion table.

Table III shows the evaluation of the sensor-based gesture recognition system's performance. The likelihood that the system will correctly identify the gesture is used to compute the system's performance.

Index value	Middle value	Ring value	Pinky value	Angle (Degrees)	Recognized Alphabet
>100	>1	1-100	>150	90	A
255	255	>200	1	0	B
<150	<150	>50	<100	30	C
1	>100	>150	1	60	D

Table -II -Performance analysis of sensor based system for gesture recognition

Table II shows the combination of voltage values used to display the letters A, B, C, and D. Similarly, the remaining alphabets are recognized using various voltage value combinations.

Index value	Middle value	Ring value	Pinky value	Recognized Alphabet
1to 50	200	>250	255	Bag
255	>220	1	<200	Welcome
1	<100	255	1to100	Beg
>100	<150	1	>50	Egg
1	<240	255	<100	Bad

Table III -Voltage values for which the corresponding word is displayed

5. Result Analysis

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	Performance (%)
1	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	87.5
2	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	100
3	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	75
4	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	87.5
5	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	100
6	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	87.5
7	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	75
8	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	100
9	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	75
10	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	☑	87.5

Table IV-Set of 8 gestures.

Table V In the current work the system is trained for a set of 8 gestures. Based on user interaction with the setup, the experiment is carried out for 10 times and the average recognition rate obtained is 87.5% across all the gestures and for each of these gestures the average recognition rate is found to be 80-90%.

6. Result and Discussions

Image preprocessing and edge detection

Before extracting features from images, they must be processed to remove unnecessary data and focus only on useful information. The preprocessing steps include:

1. Resizing: Images are resized to 100×100pixels to speed up computations.
2. Gray scale Conversion : The images are converted to grayscale to simplify the data.
3. Binary Conversion: The grayscale image is transformed into a binary image for better feature extraction.
4. Skin Color Detection: The YCbCr color model is used to detect skin regions in the image.
5. Edge Detection: The Canny edge detector is applied to extract important structural details while reducing the amount of data.

The Canny edge detection method is widely used in computer vision as it helps detect significant edges while reducing noise.

Image preprocessing and edge detection

Fig 2. Block diagram of Speech to Sign Language interpreter System

Fig 3. Output of skin colour detection: a) Original cropped image, b) Grey scale converted image, c) Skin colour detection output

Feature extraction

Feature Extraction in Object Detection

Feature extraction is a crucial step in any object detection system. Various methods can be used, including:

Fourier Descriptor: Captures shape information using frequency components.

Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT): Extracts key points from reference images and stores them in a database. New images are compared using the **Euclidean distance** between feature vectors to find matching objects.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA): A **dimensionality reduction technique** that transforms large data sets into a smaller set while preserving essential information.

Histogram of Oriented Gradients(HOG):

Used for **object detection** by analyzing gradient orientations.

The image is divided into small cells, and a histogram of gradients is computed.

Gradients are grouped based on magnitude and angle to form a feature descriptor.

In this study, the **HOG method** is used for feature extraction.

This technique helps detect objects by analyzing the intensity distribution and edge directions within an image.

Additionally, a **language model** in a sign interpreter can detect sign language in real time. It can analyze **hand positions** and display their meaning on a screen.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper describes an approach for recognizing the American Sign Language (ASL), that is, to provide an interface for the deaf and mute population to communicate through the internet. Machine learning is the foundation of this system. This system takes into account the several shortcomings of the current system as well as their benefits for improved system performance. It is designed to facilitate online communication for the deaf and mute people. However, there are certain restrictions on this as well. Instead of using dynamic gesture recognition, the interpreter solely employs static gestures. The ability to recognize gestures in a continuous sequence in videos is known as dynamic gesture recognition. Dynamic

Gesture recognition is a far more complicated system that has not yet been developed.

8. References

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